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The Economic Value of Women's Unpaid Labor: A Global and Indian Perspective Through Time-Use Surveys

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Abstract:

This article delves into the socio-economic contributions of women, particularly focusing on the often-overlooked value of unpaid labor. Traditionally, women's roles were confined to domestic spheres, but with economic reforms and trade liberalization, their participation in the workforce has increased. Despite this, the dual burden of paid employment and domestic responsibilities continues to weigh heavily on women, especially in developing countries like India. This paper explores the economic implications of women's unpaid work through a review of global and Indian time-use surveys. These surveys provide critical insights into how women allocate their time between paid and unpaid activities, highlighting the significant yet undervalued contributions of women to both household and national economies. By quantifying this unpaid labor, the study underscores the need for policies that recognize and address the economic value of women's work, ultimately contributing to a more equitable distribution of labor and resources.

Keywords: Labor Force Participation Rate; Women's Unpaid Labor; Time Use Surveys.

Introduction:

Women play a crucial role in the socio-economic development of any country. The pace of economic growth can be significantly accelerated by improving the status, position, and living conditions of women. Traditionally, women were confined to the domestic sphere, with their primary responsibilities revolving around household chores, childbearing, and caregiving. Employment outside the home was often frowned upon. However, with the advent of trade liberalization and economic reforms, greater opportunities have emerged for educated and professional women. Despite these advances, market competition has intensified pressures on poorer segments of society, particularly poor women. They are now expected to continue their traditional roles within the household while also seeking paid employment to supplement family income.

The work that women perform at home, in subsistence agriculture, and other non-market activities is often undervalued and unrecognized in economic terms. One of the primary reasons for this is the lack of a proper methodology to quantify such work. As a result, these contributions are typically excluded from economic calculations and are grossly undervalued when acknowledged. It is essential to develop reliable techniques to measure the non-monetary contributions of women to their families and the broader economy.

The economic value of unpaid work raises important questions about the nature of domestic labor within the context of industrial capitalism. Secombe (1973) argues that since domestic labor does not directly relate to production or market exchange, housewives do not produce "surplus value" and are therefore not exploited in the same way as wage laborers. In contrast, Dalla Costa and James (1972) assert that housework is a form of productive labor because it not only reproduces the labor force through child-rearing but also maintains the daily labor power of wage workers. Another perspective suggests that the categories of "productive" and "unproductive" labor are irrelevant to housework, which constitutes a unique economic category of its own. Despite these theoretical differences, there

is broad agreement that domestic labor is an integral and necessary part of a capitalist economy and the social relations of work (Mary Evans and David Morgan, 1979).

The Female Economic Activity Rate (FEAR) varies globally, ranging from 55.6% in Australia and 55% in Indonesia to 82.9% in Mozambique. In India, the FEAR was recorded at 42% (Human Development Report, 2001). According to the National Sample Survey Office (NSSO) 55th Round on Employment and Unemployment in India (1999-2000), in rural areas, the female work participation rate was highest at 58.6% in the 40-44 age group and exceeded 50% in the 30-54 age group. In urban areas, the highest female work participation rate was 28.5% in the 35-39 age group, with a similar rate of 28.3% in the 40-44 age group.

Despite these statistics, there has been little reduction in the burden on women to maintain and manage the household. More women are now participating in the labor force, yet they continue to shoulder the primary responsibility for home and family care. This dual burden often results in the sacrifice of personal care and leisure time. Additionally, men rarely take the initiative in sharing household responsibilities and childcare.

Literature Review:

1. Women's Role in Socio-Economic Development: Women play a pivotal role in the socio-economic development of any nation. Historically, their contributions have been confined to domestic duties, but with the advent of economic reforms, more opportunities have emerged for women in the workforce. However, this shift has also imposed a dual burden on women, who are now expected to manage both household responsibilities and paid employment. The undervaluation of women's unpaid labor is a significant issue, as it is often excluded from economic calculations, leading to a skewed understanding of their contributions to the economy (Secombe, 1973; Dalla Costa & James, 1972).

2. The Economic Value of Unpaid Labor: The economic value of unpaid domestic labor has been a subject of debate among scholars. Secombe (1973) argues that since domestic labor does not directly contribute to market production, it does not generate "surplus value" and is thus not exploited in the same way as wage labor. On the other hand, Dalla Costa and James (1972) contend that domestic labor is productive, as it reproduces the labor force and maintains the daily labor power of wage workers. This perspective highlights the integral role of domestic labor in sustaining the capitalist economy, even though it remains unrecognized and undervalued in economic terms (Evans & Morgan, 1979).

3. Time-Use Surveys: A Tool for Measuring Women's Unpaid Labor: Time-use surveys have emerged as a vital tool in quantifying the economic contributions of women, particularly in developing countries. These surveys provide detailed data on how individuals allocate their time, offering insights into the dynamics of paid and unpaid labor. In India, time-use surveys have revealed that women spend significantly more time on unpaid activities than men, highlighting the gender disparities in labor distribution. The Central Statistical Organisation's (CSO) survey in 2000, for instance, found that women spent an average of 34.6 hours per week on unpaid activities, compared to 3.6 hours for men (CSO, 2000).

4. Global Examples of Time-Use Surveys: Several countries have conducted time-use surveys to better understand the economic value of unpaid labor. In Australia, time-use surveys have been used to analyze labor force policies and monitor the status of women in the workforce. New Zealand and Japan have also conducted extensive time-use surveys, providing comprehensive data on daily life activities and highlighting the economic contributions of invisible household work. These global examples demonstrate the importance of recognizing and valuing unpaid labor in economic policies (Australian Bureau of Statistics, 1997; Statistics New Zealand, 1999; Statistics Bureau of Japan, 1976).

5. Implications for Policy and Economic Development: Recognizing the economic value of unpaid labor has significant implications for policy-making. By accurately quantifying women's

contributions, governments can develop more equitable labor policies that address gender disparities in the workforce. Additionally, recognizing unpaid labor in economic calculations can lead to better resource allocation, ensuring that women's contributions are adequately compensated and valued. This, in turn, can contribute to more sustainable and inclusive economic development (World Bank, 1995).

Findings

Time Use Surveys in Global and Indian Contexts

In recent years, time-use surveys have gained importance, particularly in developing countries, as a tool to quantify the economic contributions of women. These surveys provide comprehensive data on how individuals allocate their time on a daily and weekly basis, offering insights into the dynamics of work and life. The information collected is free from socio-cultural bias since it encompasses all activities over 24 hours, ensuring that no aspect of daily life is overlooked.

It is widely recognized that non-market household production is an economic activity closely linked to market production, especially in decisions related to time allocation between paid and unpaid work. Several studies have been conducted to explore the time allocation between paid and unpaid work of women in India, including:

1. Ogale and Ranawat (1973): Investigated the use and value of leisure time among 140 homemakers, both employed and unemployed.
2. Dhesi and Sandhu (1975): Studied factors affecting time utilization in household activities by rural homemakers in Narangawali village, Ludhiana district.
3. Bhatnagar and Saxena (1988): Examined time utilization patterns among tribal and non-tribal women in home and farm activities.
4. Lakshmi Devi (1988): Analyzed the daily time utilization patterns of rural women in Atkur village for household activities.
5. Krishnan and Kumary (1989): Studied the average time disposition of rural labor households in a Kerala village.
6. Malathi (1994): Explored the time allocation to non-market work among urban women in Madras during 1980-81.
7. World Bank (1995): Conducted extensive research on time spent by men and women on market and non-market activities in various countries.
8. Kishtwari (1999): Investigated time utilization patterns of Gaddi tribal women in Himachal Pradesh.
9. Central Statistical Organisation (CSO) (2000): Conducted a macro-level time use survey covering 18,591 households in six major Indian states (Gujarat, Haryana, Madhya Pradesh, Meghalaya, Orissa, and Tamil Nadu) from July 1998 to June 1999.

The Central Statistics Organisation Survey

The CSO's macro-level time use survey (2000) provides an extensive overview of time allocation patterns across six major Indian states. The survey revealed that, on average, males spent about 3.6 hours per week on extended SNA (System of National Accounts) activities, while females spent 34.6 hours. Unpaid activities accounted for 51% of women's time, compared to only 33% for men.

Human Development Index of the World Bank

The World Bank's Human Development Report (1995) highlighted the gender disparities in the distribution of work. It found that women carry 53% of the total burden of work in developing countries and 51% in industrialized nations. In industrial countries, two-thirds of men's work time is

spent on paid SNA activities, while for women, this is reversed, with most of their work remaining unpaid, unrecognized, and undervalued.

Objectives of Time Use Surveys

The objectives of time-use surveys vary depending on the country. For instance, Nepal's first budget study in 1976-77 aimed to:

1. Provide insights into the dynamics of development by studying the shift of activities from the household sector to the market and vice versa.
2. Obtain a more accurate estimate of GDP and women's contribution to the economy.
3. Monetize voluntary community services.

Findings of Time Use Surveys

The findings from time-use surveys have been revealing. For example, the survey in Nepal showed that GDP could more than double if all goods and services produced for household consumption and maintenance activities were accounted for. Women were found to contribute 63% of the total amount and 27.5% of regular GDP, with 58.3% of their contribution in non-market (but within SNA) activities and 92.8% in household maintenance.

Global Examples of Time-Use Surveys

In Australia, time-use surveys have been conducted since 1987, with subsequent surveys in 1992 and 1997. These surveys were developed to analyze labor force policies for women, complement data on paid employment, and allow the government to monitor the status of women in the labor force concerning family and household responsibilities.

New Zealand also conducted a pilot time use survey in 1990, followed by a full survey from July 1998 to June 1999. The survey identified various aspects of daily life, including the actual hours spent on paid work, time spent on health and maintenance activities, and the characteristics of people participating in voluntary work.

In Japan, time-use surveys have been conducted since 1976, with the Statistics Bureau and NHK (Japan Broadcasting Corporation) as the main organizations involved. These surveys provide comprehensive data on people's daily lives and have been instrumental in understanding the economic value of invisible household work.

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